

Moroccan actinobacteria with promising activity against toxic cyanobacteria

Microcystis aeruginosa

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Abstract

In recent decades, harmful cyanobacterial blooms (HCBs) have become a severe hazard for human health mainly in drinking water resources and are responsible for serious ecological disturbances in freshwater ecosystems. The present study aims to explore the potential of actinobacteria isolated from a sediment samples collected from Moroccan salt river to control

HCBs mainly through *Microcystis aeruginosa* lysis. In order to investigate the possible anti-cyanobacterial response mechanisms, the antioxidant enzyme activities of *M. aeruginosa* cells were analyzed. Anti-cyanobacterial activity was tested using the agar cylinder method against the toxic cyanobacteria *Microcystis aeruginosa*. Among the twenty-three isolates tested, only one showed promising anti-cyanobacterial activities with inhibition zone (ZI) equal to 22.00 mm, minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) equal to 19.53 mg/L and minimum bactericidal concentration MBC equal to 39.06 mg/L. Phylogenetic analysis of the near-complete 16S rRNA gene sequence indicated that the strain DS1R1 belongs to the genus *Streptomyces* and has highest similarity (100%) to *Streptomyces* sp. Indeed, *M. aeruginosa* growth, chlorophyll-a and protein content were significantly reduced by *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract. Superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and malondialdehyde (MDA) were significantly elevated after treatment with *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract. These experimental findings provided insights in the development of a new eco-friendly procedure based on the use of actinobacteria for toxic cyanobacterial blooms bio-control.

Keywords Anti-cyanobacterial activity - Bio-control – Actinobacteria - Cyanobacterial blooms - *Microcystis aeruginosa*.

1. Introduction

Due to the associated problems, blooms of blue green algae (cyanobacteria) became one of the most important ecological research topics (Harke et al. 2016; Jia et al. 2019; Janssen 2019). Harmful cyanobacterial blooms (HCBs) occur mainly in the warm season with dominance of the genus *Microcystis* which is capable of producing various microcystins congeners (Catherine et al. 2013). Various approaches have been developed to control or prevent HCBs, based on physical, chemical and biological processes (Park et al. 2017; Sun et al. 2018b; Zohdi and Abbaspour 2019). Chemical agents such as copper sulphate, potassium chloride, endothall and other chemical molecules have been applied (Seder-Colomina et al. 2013; Pohl et al. 2015; Sandrini et al. 2015; Nagai et al. 2016; Huh and Ahn 2017). Mechanical and physical control refer to the use of ultrasound, artificial mixing and ultraviolet (Visser et al. 2016; Marzbali et al. 2017; Park et al. 2017). Biological agents include the introduction of herbivorous fishes, algae, macrophyte and microorganisms (Visser et al. 2005; Gerphagnon et al. 2015; Wichelen et al. 2016; Coloma et al. 2017; Montemezzani et al. 2017; Liu et al. 2018). However, none of those methods has been successfully used due to unforeseen ecological consequences, the high

costs, high energy consumption and low efficiency (Gao and Xie 2011; Zerrifi et al. 2018). Consequently, the research on more environmentally friendly and low cost approaches for the control of HCBs is urgently needed. Natural compounds such as proteins, pigments, fatty acid compounds, amino acids, antibiotics, alkaloids and peptides have been isolated from many microorganisms and tested to control cyanobacterial blooms (Sun et al. 2018a). Actinobacteria, especially, the genus *Streptomyces*, are amongst the microorganisms most predominant producer of bioactive secondary molecules with diverse biological activities, namely antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anticancer, anti-biofouling, anti-malarial, anti-parasitic and antioxidant (Manivasagan et al. 2016; Yadav et al. 2018; Law et al. 2019). Moreover, some actinobacteria metabolites have been proven to inhibit bloom-forming cyanobacteria (Sun et al. 2018a). Algicidal agents, such as tryptoline and tryptamine extracted from *Streptomyces eurocidicus* JXJ-0089 (Zhang et al. 2016); NIG355 compound, purified and identified from the marine actinobacteria *Streptomyces malaysiensis* O4-6 (Zheng et al. 2012), have been reported. Nevertheless, the search for bioactive actinobacterial compounds with anti-cyanobacterial potency is still at the embryonic stage because of the difficulties associated to their isolation, purification, identification and functional characterization. The present study aims to valorise actinobacteria from sediment samples collected from a salt river in Morocco, concerning the anti-cyanobacterial actinobacteria activity. Our work reports the effects of Moroccan actinobacteria on *M. aeruginosa*, a cyanobacteria species that commonly forms HCBs in Moroccan freshwaters.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Isolation and maintenance of strains

Twenty-three actinobacteria were isolated from a sediment samples collected from a salt river in Demnate region (31°48'04.1"N 7°00'31.0"W), Morocco, by using serial dilution technique. The purified strains were grown on Bennett's agar medium (beef extract 1 g·L⁻¹; glucose 10 g·L⁻¹; peptone 2 g·L⁻¹; yeast extract 1 g·L⁻¹ and bacteriological agar 15 g·L⁻¹) at 28°C for 2 weeks and stored as glycerol suspensions (25%, v/v) at -20 °C.

2.2. Cyanobacteria strain and culture conditions

The tested *M. aeruginosa* was sampled from the eutrophic reservoir Lalla Takerkoust in bloom period (October) and then the strain was isolated, separated into singles cells and maintained in culture in BG13 medium (NaNO₃ 1.5 g·L⁻¹ NaHCO₃ 1.7 g·L⁻¹; K₂HPO₄ 31 mg·L⁻¹; MgSO₄·7H₂O 75 mg·L⁻¹; CaCl₂·H₂O 36 mg·L⁻¹; Na₂CO₃ 20 mg·L⁻¹; citric acid 6 mg·L⁻¹; ferric

ammonium citrate 6 g·L⁻¹; disodium magnesium EDTA 1 mg·L⁻¹; H₃BO₃ 2.86 mg·L⁻¹; Mn₂Cl₂·4H₂O 1.81 mg·L⁻¹; ZnSO₄·7H₂O 220 µg·L⁻¹; Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O 390 g·L⁻¹; CuSO₄·5H₂O 80 mg·L⁻¹ and CoCl₂·6H₂O 40 µg·L⁻¹) under controlled conditions (temperature of 26 ± 2 °C, light intensity of 4000 lx·m⁻² s⁻¹, and a light/dark cycle of 15 h/9 h) according to the protocol described by Zerrifi et al. (2019).

2.3. Screening of anti-cyanobacterial activity

2.3.1. Qualitative assay for anti-cyanobacterial activity

Actinobacteria isolates were cultivated on Bennett's agar medium. After 2-week of incubation at 28°C, agar discs were cut out with a cork borer (6 mm diameter) and placed on the surface of BG 13 medium previously inoculated with *M. aeruginosa*. In order to allow the diffusion of produced actinobacteria secondary metabolites, the prepared plates were kept at 4°C for 4h. Copper sulphate was employed as positive control. Each test was performed in triplicate to statistically validate the findings.

2.3.2. Quantitative assay for anti-cyanobacterial activity

a. Preparation of crude extract

The strain with the highest inhibitory activity in the qualitative assay was subjected to ethyl acetate extraction according to the protocol previously described by Sengupta et al. (2015). After cultivation in liquid Bennett medium at 28 °C with agitation (150 rpm) during an incubation period of 10 days, the culture medium of the selected actinobacteria was centrifuged at 6000×G for 15 minutes and the supernatant was collected and filtered through n^o. 2 filter paper under reduced pressure. The filtrate was extracted with ethyl acetate in the ratio of 1:1 (v/v) twice and the residual ethyl acetate was concentrated by rotary evaporation at 40°C.

b. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) Determination

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for ethyl acetate extract was determined by broth microdilution method following the NCCLS guidelines M7-A4 (NCCLS. 1997). Each well of 96-well plate contained 100 µL of tested cyanobacteria culture in exponential growth phase (3×10⁶ cells/mL) and 100 µL of extract dissolved in 1% of DMSO to obtain a concentration range from 2.44 to 5000 µg/mL. Similar concentration range of copper sulphate and DMSO (1%) were used as positive and negative control, respectively. Plates were incubated for five days under conditions of culture chamber already mentioned above. Subsequently, 100 µL of each well medium with no visible cyanobacterial growth was inoculated in BG 13 medium in

order to determinate the Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC). Each test was performed in BG 13 media in triplicate.

2.4. Taxonomic identification of the active actinobacteria strain

For DNA extraction, colonies of the active isolate were grown on M1 agar (per liter of seawater: 10 g of soluble starch, 4 g of yeast extract, 2 g of peptone and 17 g of agar), picked up with a loop and suspended in 100 μ L of TE Buffer. Genomic DNA was extracted with the EZNA® Bacterial DNA Kit (Omega Biotek, Norcross, GA), following the manufacturer's instructions, with some protocol optimizations: (i) in the lysozyme addition step, the samples were incubated at 37 °C for 30 min; (ii) in the optional step for mechanical cell membrane lysis, two zirconia beads (2.3 mm diameter) were added along with the glass beads provided in the kit, and the samples were vortexed for 10 min; (iii) incubation with proteinase K was performed with a stock solution at the concentration of 10 mg/mL instead of the solution provided in the kit and was extended to 2 h (iv) the centrifugation speed was increased in all steps from 10,000 g to 13,000 g; (v) in the final step of DNA elution, 25 μ L of Elution Buffer was added to the HiBind® DNA Mini Column instead of 50-100 μ L, as indicated in the protocol. 16S rRNA gene was amplified by PCR using the universal primers 27F (5'-GAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'-TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'). The PCR mixture contained (in a final volume of 10 μ L): 5 μ L of Taq PCR Master Mix (Qiagen, Valencia, CA), 1 μ L of each primer (2 μ M) and 3 μ L of DNA template. Negative controls consisted in substituting in the PCR mixture the DNA template by 3 μ L of Nuclease-Free Water. PCR was performed in an Applied Biosystems ThermoCycler (Applied Biosystems Inc., Foster City, CA, USA) with the following conditions: initial denaturation at 95 °C for 15 min, followed by 30 cycles at 94 °C for 30 s, 48 °C for 90 s, 72 °C for 90 s and a final extension at 72 °C for 10 min. PCR products were separated on a 1.5% agarose gel containing SYBR Safe (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA), at 150 V for 30 min. Purification and sequencing of the amplified DNA was made by GenCore, i3S (Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Portugal). The 16S rRNA sequences were analyzed using the Geneious software (version 11.1.4, Biomatters, Auckland, New Zealand). The resulting consensus sequences were compared to the GenBank database using the blast algorithm and to the databases, EzTaxon (<http://www.ezbiocloud.net/>) and Ribosomal Database Project (<https://rdp.cme.msu.edu/index.jsp>). The 16S rRNA gene sequence of the isolate was deposited in GenBank (NCBI, Maryland, USA) under the accession number MT320758. For construction

of a phylogenetic tree, the sequence of the isolate and of its ten closest neighbor sequences in Genbank were aligned using the MUSCLE alignment tool from the Geneious software. The alignment was used to generate a Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree with 1000 bootstraps based on the Tamura-Nei model. The phylogenetic tree was performed using the Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis program Version 7.0 (MEGA 7) (Kumar et al. 2016).

2.5. Physiological effects of the active actinobacteria strain on *M. aeruginosa*

The physiological effects in *M. aeruginosa* cells were studied in Erlenmeyer flasks (150 mL) containing 80 mL of the cyanobacteria culture with initial density of 2×10^6 cells/mL (the exponential growth phase). *M. aeruginosa* was exposed in triplicate, to an extract of the most active actinobacteria dissolved in 1% of DMSO, at two different concentrations (determined MIC and MBC concentrations), copper sulphate used as a positive control at determined MIC and MBC concentrations and a negative control (DMSO). An untreated *M. aeruginosa* culture was analysed in parallel. In order to determinate the actinobacteria effect on the tested cyanobacteria, an estimation of inhibition and growth was done by counting of cells everyday using a hemocytometer under a microscope during a follow-up period of 6 days (Sbiyyaa et al. 1998).

The inhibition rate (IR %) was estimated through the following Eq. 1 :

$$\text{IR}(\%) = ((N_u - N_t) / N_u) \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

N_u and N_t represent the cell concentrations in the untreated and treatment samples, respectively.

While, the growth rate was calculated using the following Eq. 2 (Xu et al. 2010):

$$\mu = (\ln N_l - \ln N_f) / \Delta t \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

N_l and N_f (cells/mL) are the cell densities at the last and first day of the test, respectively and Δt indicates the time of the test.

Chlorophyll-a concentration was measured spectrophotometrically every 48h (Wang et al. 2010) and calculated using the method described by Lichtenthaler and Wellburn (1983). Briefly, 5 mL of the culture sample was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 15 min to collect algal cells. Cells were then re-suspended with boiling ethanol (95%). The three replicas were incubated at 4°C for 48 h. Subsequently, another centrifugation for 5 min at 5000 rpm was

performed to eliminate the pellet. The supernatant optical density (OD) was read at different wavelengths absorbance (470, 649 and 665 nm). Chlorophyll-a concentration was calculated by the following Eq. 3.

$$[\text{Chl-a}] = 13.95 \times \text{DO665} - 6.88 \times \text{DO649} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

The enzyme extracts were prepared using the protocol described by Li et al. (2016). Briefly, *M. aeruginosa* cells were harvested by centrifugation at $4000 \times g$ for 25 min. The pellet was re-suspended in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.5) containing 1% (w/v) polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). Then the cells were disrupted and homogenized by an ultrasonic cell pulverizer for 5 min in an ice bath. The homogenate was then centrifuged $10,000 \times g$ at 4°C for 10 min. The supernatant was used for total protein measurement and antioxidant enzyme activity assays. Protein content was determined every 48h according to Bradford (1976) method. Shortly, 100 μl of the enzyme extract was added to 2 ml of Bradford's reagent and incubated at room temperature in obscurity for 20 min. Furthermore, a mixture of the assay buffer (100 μl) and the Bradford's reagent (2 ml) was used as a blank. The absorbance was read at 595 nm and the protein content was calculated from a calibration curve of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA).

In order to investigate the cyanobacterial biochemical characteristics in *M. aeruginosa* cells, Superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and malondialdehyde (MDA) contents were determined. The SOD activity was determined according to methods described by Beauchamp and Fridovich (1971). The reaction mixture contained 0.8 mL PBS solution (50 mM, pH 7.8), 0.3 mL methionine solution (130 mM), 0.3 mL Na_2EDTA solution (100 μM), 0.3 mL riboflavin solution (20 μM), 0.3 mL nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT) solution (750 μM), and 1 mL enzyme extract for a total volume of 3 mL. As SOD has the ability to inhibit the photochemical reduction of NBT, this assay utilized negative controls (silver paper wrapped around the test tube to mimic fully dark condition without any photochemical reduction of NBT), positive controls (deficiency of SOD activity in light with full photochemical reduction of NBT) and treatment groups (in light with SOD inhibition on photochemical reduction of NBT). The absorbencies of all experimental tubes were measured at 560 nm after a 20 min irradiance of 40–60 mmol photons. $\text{m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$. One unit of SOD activity was defined as the amount of enzyme that inhibited 50% of photochemical reduction of NBT. CAT activity was assayed by absorbance decrease being proportional to the breakdown rate of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) at 240 nm according to the method of Rao et al. (1996).

Lipid peroxidation was reflected by the MDA level and determined according to the work by Du et al. (2017). Samples were collected and centrifuged at 4000 ×g for 20 min. The cell pellets were homogenized with 2 mL of 10% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and centrifuged at 12000 × g for 10 min at 4°C. After centrifugation, 2 mL of the supernatant was mixed with 2 mL of 0.6% thiobarbituric acid (in 10% TCA) and heated in boiling water for 15 min. The reaction was stopped by transferring the reaction tubes into an ice bath. Following cooling, the samples were then centrifuged at 12000 ×g for 10 min. The absorbance of the supernatant was measured at 532, 600 and 450 nm, taking a mixture of 2 mL ultrapure water and 2 mL 0.6% TBA as reference. The MDA level (µmol/L) was calculated according to Eq. 4:

$$\text{MDA} = 6.45 \times \text{OD}_{532} - \text{OD}_{600} - 0.56 \times \text{OD}_{450} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

2.6. Statistical analysis

The results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (S.D.). Each experiment was done in triplicate. The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests were used to determine data normality. Statistical analyses were performed by SigmaPlot 12.5 software for Windows and Microsoft Excel 2013. One-way and two-way ANOVA with the Tukey test was used to analyze the differences between experimental groups and the control. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 21.0 statistical software. Values of $p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.005$ were considered for statistical validation.

3. Results

3.1. Evaluation of actinobacteria anti-cyanobacterial activity

The anti-cyanobacterial activity of actinobacteria was examined qualitatively by the application of agar discs diffusion method. After one week of incubation, the measurement of the inhibition zones has been performed. The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests demonstrated that the diameters of ZI values were normally distributed. The results show that among the twenty-three tested actinobacteria isolates, only one strain, DS1R1, recorded an activity against the cyanobacteria *M. aeruginosa*, with a growth inhibition diameter of 22.00 ± 1.00 mm (Fig. 1), while the cooper sulphate, used as positive control, showed strong activity against *M. aeruginosa* with inhibition zone of 45.34 ± 0.52 mm. In order to determine the anti-cyanobacterial activity quantitatively, an ethyl extract of the strain showing positive activity was obtained and the MIC and MBC were determined after 7 days of incubation. The results show that the ethyl extract of the postive strain displayed a great effectiveness, with a MIC of

19.53 mg/L and a MBC of 39.06 mg/L. Moreover, the positive control showed an important potency (MIC = MBC = 3.12 mg/L).

Fig. 1 Anti-cyanobacterial activity of actinobacteria against *M. aeruginosa* on solid media. **A.** Inactive actinobacteria strain; **B.** Active actinobacteria strain (strain DS1R1); **C.** Copper sulphate.

3.2. Taxonomic study of the active actinobacteria

The 16S rRNA gene sequence and its subsequent phylogenetic analysis of strain DS1R1, showing significant anti-cyanobacterial activity, revealed that this strain is a member of the genus *Streptomyces*, closely clustering with the species *S. netropsis* and *S. syringium* (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Phylogenetic tree of the DS1R1 strain and their GenBank nearest neighbours. Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree was performed in MEGA 7 using 12 sequences with 1373 bp. The

bootstrap method was used with 1000 replications. Bootstraps values shown at nodes support the branching order of the tree (values below 60% are not shown). The GenBank accession numbers are represented in parenthesis. *Bacillus subtilis* X-18 was used as an outgroup.

3.3. Effects of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract on *M. aeruginosa* cells

3.3.1. Effect on *M. aeruginosa* growth

The effect of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract, tested at two concentrations (MIC and MBC, 19.53 and 39.06 mg/L, respectively), on *M. aeruginosa* growth was analysed in terms of IR (%) and μ (Table 1 and Fig. 3, respectively). The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests indicated that the IR and μ values were normally distributed. During the entire follow-up period, copper sulphate, used as positive control, showed a strong inhibition; IR was more than 70% at the first day of treatment and increased gradually up to a value greater than 98% at the end of the experiment (Table 1). The inhibition rate of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract at the MBC (39.06 mg/L) and MIC (19.53 mg/L) were statistically similar to that of positive control on the end of the experiment. The IR was more than 73% and 49%, respectively, on the first day of experiment. The IR values increased up to 95% and 98% at 19.53 mg/L and 39.06 mg/L, respectively on the last day of the experiment. Under standard culturing conditions and in the negative control, *M. aeruginosa* growth rates and generation time were 0.56 day⁻¹ and 1.23 day⁻¹, respectively. The *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract had a strong effect on the tested cyanobacteria at both used concentrations. At MIC, the cyanobacteria strain was able to reproduce but in a very weak way; it required 17.8 days to have a new generation, and the growth rate decreased significantly with μ value of 0.04 day⁻¹. Interestingly, the effects of MBC on *M. aeruginosa* growth rate and generation time was statistically similar to that of the positive control. The tested cyanobacterium became unable to reproduce and the μ value were less than -0.18 day⁻¹.

Table 1 Inhibition rates of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract on *M. aeruginosa*

Treatments	Inhibition rate (%)						
	Time (days)						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
MIC	0±0	49.18±1.24 ^b	64.02±0.23 ^b	77.97±0.07 ^b	83.89±0.15 ^b	94.83±0.14 ^b	95.69±0.1 ^b
MBC	0±0	73.93±0.49 ^c	89.69±0.12 ^c	94.34±0.21 ^c	97.52±0.08 ^c	98.48±0.07 ^b	98.85±0.02 ^b
Copper sulphate	0±0	70.57±2.06 ^c	88.92±0.24 ^c	94.12±0.07 ^c	97.54±0.05 ^c	98.5±0.02 ^b	98.87±0.01 ^b
DMSO	0±0	-0.33±0.49 ^a	0.08±1.67 ^a	0±0.39 ^a	-1.01±0.6 ^a	-1.11±2.27 ^a	-0.14±0.87 ^a

Each value representing mean \pm SD of 3 replicates. Means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0,001$).

Fig. 3 Effect of MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration) and MBC (Minimum Bactericidal Concentration) of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract on the growth rate of *M. aeruginosa*. Means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0,001$). Each value representing mean \pm SD of 3 replicates.

3.3.2. Effects on *M. aeruginosa* Chlorophyll-a and protein contents

Chlorophyll-a and protein contents were determined to evaluate the effect of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract on *M. aeruginosa* cells (Fig. 4). At the beginning of experiment, the chlorophyll-a and protein contents were similar in all treatments. For the untreated culture and the negative control, the chlorophyll-a and protein contents increased significantly with experimental time; whereas, *M. aeruginosa* chlorophyll-a and protein content was significantly decreased by both used concentrations of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract. Compared to the untreated culture and the negative control, the contents of chlorophyll-a and protein decreased significantly after the second day of exposure to *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract. The responses of chlorophyll-a and protein contents exposed to the MIC and MBC were quite similar to copper sulphate used as positive control, during the 6 days of experiment.

Fig. 4 Effect of *Streptomyces sp. DS1R1* ethyl acetate extract on *M. aeruginosa* chlorophyll-a (A) and protein content (B). Each value representing mean \pm SD of three replicates. Means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0,001$).

3.3.3. Effects of *Streptomyces sp. DS1R1* extract on SOD, CAT activities and MDA concentration in *M. aeruginosa* cells

SOD is the first defense against ROS (Reactive Oxygen Species) among antioxidant systems. The activity of the antioxidant enzyme SOD was investigated to determine whether *Streptomyces sp. DS1R1* extract affects the antioxidant system. The results are shown in Fig. 5A. The results showed that SOD activities in cyanobacterial cells of the untreated cultures and negative control were stable during the 6 days of experiment, which showed a significant difference compared to the positive control (copper sulphate) and the MIC and MBC treatments. After 48 h of exposure, the SOD activity in cyanobacterial cells treated with 19.53 and 39.06 mg/L of *Streptomyces sp. DS1R1* extract decreased. However, the SOD activity at 39.06 mg/L (MBC concentration) was higher than that at 19.53 mg/L (MIC concentration). Thereafter, the SOD activity began to decrease gradually along time in the positive control and treatment groups. CAT is the second defense against ROS. As shown in Fig. 5B, the CAT activity in *M. aeruginosa* cells exposed to *Streptomyces sp. DS1R1* extract exhibited a significant increase, while the CAT activities in the untreated cultures and the negative control remained unchanged over time. The differences between treated and untreated cultures were

apparent after 48 h of exposure. The CAT activity at 39.06 mg/L of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract (MBC concentration) was higher than that at 19.53 mg/L (MIC concentration).

Fig. 5 Superoxide dismutase (A) and catalase (B) activities in *M. aeruginosa* cells after treatment with *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract. Means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0,001$). Each value representing mean \pm SD of 3 replicates.

MDA is the final product of lipid peroxidation in organisms and is generally used as an indicator of lipid peroxidation. As shown in Fig. 6, the MDA level in *M. aeruginosa* cells exposed to 19.53 and 39.06 mg/L *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract exhibited a significant increase since the fourth day of treatment, while the MDA level in the untreated culture and the negative control remained unchanged over time. The maximal MDA value was 134 μ mol/L at the sixth day of treatment with 39.06 mg/L of *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 extract, which was 2.79 times higher than that of the negative control.

Fig. 6 Malondialdehyde level in *M. aeruginosa* cells after treatment with *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract. Means with different letters are significantly different ($p < 0,001$). Each value representing mean \pm SD of 3 replicates.

4. Discussion

Actinobacteria are one of the most predominant producers of bioactive compounds and can be a promising alternative eco-friendly solutions for HCBs control (Harir et al. 2018; Sun et al. 2018a). Hence, we proceeded to evaluate the anti-cyanobacterial activity of actinobacteria isolated from a soil and sediment sample collected from Morocco. The qualitative screening in solid medium using the agar cylinder method revealed that among the twenty-three tested isolates, one strain showed an important positive anti-cyanobacterial activity against the tested cyanobacterial species *M. aeruginosa* with inhibition zone of 22.00 mm. Phylogenetic analysis of the near-complete 16S rRNA sequence of the strain showing evident anti-cyanobacterial activity, strain DS1R1, indicated that it is affiliated with the genus *Streptomyces*, which is broadly known by its antimicrobial activities. Previous studies reported that *Streptomyces* genus produce 70–80% of the total derived bioactive compounds, with many of these compounds exhibiting antimicrobial activity (Bérdy 2005; Manteca et al. 2008; Procópio et al. 2012; Dhanasekaran and Jiang 2016; Manimaran et al. 2017; Tangjitjaroenkun 2018; Sivarajan et al. 2019; Soundarya et al. 2020). For example, Al-Ansari et al. (2019) studied the antimicrobial activity of five *Streptomyces* ethyl acetate extracts and showed broad spectrum of antibacterial activities against Gram-negative bacteria, namely *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis*,

Enterobacter aerogenes and *Escherichia coli*. In another study, Baskaran et al. (2016) observed that *Streptomyces parvulus* DOSMB-D105 ethyl acetate extract conferred a great activity against *Pseudomonas* sp. (27.66 mm), followed by *Proteus* sp. (22.66 mm) and *E. coli* (20.33 mm). Similar results were obtained by Keerthana et al. (2019), who found that the *Streptomyces* KAV 2 ethyl acetate fraction had an important antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*, *S. flexneri* and *P. vulgaris*. Moreover, Elkholy et al. (2019) showed that *Streptomyces manipurensis* H 21 methanolic extract exhibited inhibitory activity against *K. pneumoniae* ATCC 700603 with inhibition zone of 17 mm. On the other hand, Kalyani et al. (2019) investigated the antimicrobial activity of the genus *Streptomyces* sp. NLKPB45 ethyl acetate extract on Gram-negative bacteria and reported a moderate effect on the tested bacteria, with inhibition zones of 6 mm and 9 mm against *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*, respectively. With respect to the activity against cyanobacteria, Phankhajon et al. (2016) evaluated a *Streptomyces rameus* extract, and revealed that it had an important capacity to inhibit *M. aeruginosa*, exhibiting an inhibition zone diameter of 23 mm. In our study, we also show that *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract has a high effectiveness against *M. aeruginosa*, inducing an inhibition zone with a similar diameter to that reported for *Streptomyces rameus* extract and showing MIC and MBC values of 19.53 mg/L and 39.06 mg/L, respectively. Recent study reported that the ethyl acetate extract of *Streptomyces* sp. strain Al-Dhabi-97 isolated from the marine region of Saudi Arabia revealed moderate potency against Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumoniae* and *E. coli* with MIC values of 500 mg/L, 500 mg/L and 250 mg/L, respectively (Al-Dhabi et al. 2020). Akhter et al. (2018) showed that active compounds isolated from marine *Streptomyces*, *S. pratensis*, recorded MIC values ranging from 16 to 100 mg/L against *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*.

The growth inhibition, chlorophyll-a and protein content of *M. aeruginosa*, were significantly decreased after *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract treatment. This decrease attributed to the presence of active substances in *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract, which were detrimental to the metabolism of *M. aeruginosa* cells. A recent study showed that chlorophyll-a reduction occurred more than 60% after treatment of *M. aeruginosa* with *Streptomyces* sp. HJC-D1 cell-free medium (Kong et al. 2020). Luo et al. (2013) observed that *Streptomyces* sp. L74 aqueous extract exhibited a 62.67 % algicidal rate on *M. aeruginosa*. They reported that the active algicidal compound isolated from *Streptomyces* sp. L74 cultures was identified as a triterpenoid saponin. An active algicidal compound purified from *Streptomyces jiujiangensis* JXJ 0074, identified as 2'-deoxyadenosine, showed high anti-

cyanobacterial activity on *M. aeruginosa*, causing crumpling, perforation and decrease of chlorophyll-a in the cyanobacteria cells (Zhang et al. 2015a). Likewise, two indole derivatives namely tryptamine and tryptoline produced by *Streptomyces eurocidicus* JXJ-0089 exhibited a greater anti-cyanobacterial activity against *Microcystis* sp. and some other harmful cyanobacterial strains (Zhang et al. 2016). Zheng et al. (2012) purified and identified a compound, named NIG355, from the marine actinomycete *Streptomyces malaysiensis* O4-6, which showed high algicidal activity against *P. globosa*. The separation and identification of the anti-cyanobacterial active compounds produced by our *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 strain is still under investigation and could be revealed in future work.

SOD, CAT and MDA are three important cell antioxidases that protect organisms against damages caused by oxygen-free radicals. In other studies, interference with SOD and CAT activities and MDA level in *M. aeruginosa* cells was also observed in response to triterpenoid saponin isolated from *Streptomyces* sp. L74 (Luo et al. 2013) and 2'-deoxyadenosine purified from *S. jiujiangensis* JXJ 0074 (Zhang et al. 2015b). Zhang et al. (2016) reported that tryptamine and tryptoline produced by *Streptomyces eurocidicus* JXJ-0089 induced an increase of the intracellular oxidant contents in the tested cyanobacteria cells. Similar results are also reported using other treatments extracted from other organisms, such as glyphosate (Wu et al. 2016), juglone (5-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone) (Hou et al. 2019), heptanoic acid and benzoic acid (Chai et al. 2018), 17 β -estradiol (Bai et al. 2019), pyrogallol (Wang et al. 2016) and fenoxaprop-p-ethyl (Du et al. 2017) on *M. aeruginosa*.

5. Conclusion

After screening of twenty-three Moroccan actinobacteria for their anti-cyanobacterial activity and exploring their mechanisms of growth inhibition, the results showed that *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract had a high effectiveness against the toxic cyanobacteria *M. aeruginosa*. Under *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 ethyl acetate extract treatment the SOD and CAT activities were increased and the treatment caused MDA levels to change. In view of the above results, we conclude that *Streptomyces* sp. DS1R1 can be a promising source of anti-cyanobacteria compounds. Despite the challenges encountered during the enrichment, isolation, purification and identification process, the results of its use in the control of cyanobacteria blooms may worth the effort and the investment. Therefore, it is required to identify the active algicidal compounds regarding their application in the control and treatment of HCBs in various environments. Overall, this study provides a promising lead to the use of actinobacterial

compounds to control bloom-forming cyanobacteria. Nevertheless, before large scale application, we recommend that in-depth studies concerning the mechanisms of action of these actinobacterial compounds against cyanobacteria be conducted in mesocosm systems and natural field conditions to assess that are not harmful to the environment.

Conflict of interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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